

MULTI-OBJECTIVE INFUSION OPTIMIZATION IN VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING (VARTM) USING GENETIC ALGORITHMS

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1 Introduction

The challenges related to processing of composite components are a focus of current research as the complexity of parts increases constantly. The infusion stage in Liquid Composites Moulding (LCM), such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) and Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM), involves several challenging aspects regarding product quality and cost. These aspects have to be treated simultaneously as both contribute significantly to the evaluation of process success. Single-objective infusion optimization has been addressed in the literature focusing mostly on the minimization of filling time in RTM process. This has been addressed using gradient based techniques optimizing the initial resin temperature and initial speed injection [1] and Genetic Algorithms (GA) optimizing gate and vent locations [2-5]. The Branch and bound search method and graph-based two phase optimization heuristics have been implemented for the same purpose obtaining improvement in computational efficiency compared to Evolutionary Strategies [6-7]. Multi-objective optimization of the RTM filling problem has been investigated using a cascade algorithm [8-10] in a setup that accounts for gate and vent locations in order to minimize filling time and number of vents considering also a probabilistic forecast of race tracking and GAs [11-13] in which minimization of filling time and infusion related defects have been used as the objectives. The optimization of the VARTM process has not been addressed yet in the literature. The present paper describes a procedure to find optimal non-isothermal filling and gate configuration of a C composite section model using a genetic algorithm (GA) suitable for multi-objective problems in order to minimize both filling time and degree of cure at the end of the filling stage.

2. Multi objective infusion optimization using GA

2.1 GA for Multi-objective optimization

A GA for multi-objective optimization was adapted in this study [24]. The algorithm takes as input the number of generations, number of individuals per population, the number of individuals used for reproduction and elitism, the size of Pareto front, the number of objectives, and the cross-over and mutation probabilities. The outputs of the algorithm are the objectives values for each individual and the Pareto front at each generation. Four benchmark multi-objective problems have been selected to verify the behaviour of the GA; a simple convex problem proposed by Schaffer [15], one convex and one non convex problem proposed by Zitzler [16] and one non convex problem proposed by Fonseca [17].

Table 1 reports the parameters of the GA for the benchmark studies. In all the problems the Pareto size was fixed at 50 individuals, the crossover probability at 0.5 and mutation probability at 0.005. It has been observed that the GA approximates successfully and gradually the non-dominated set in all cases. In the Schaffer problem the solution converges after only 10 generations and the approximation is entirely satisfactory. For the two Zitzler problems the convergence occurs within 100 generations resulting in a very close approximation of the theoretical front. In the most complex of the benchmarks, the Fonseca problem, the GA requires 150 generations to converge. Although the approximation is close to the theoretical front, small errors can be observed in the final Pareto front. Reproducibility tests have shown that the results of the GA are not sensitive to the random seed, indicating the robustness and reliability of the methodology and the implementation (Fig. 1). Performance comparisons with established software implementation of multi-objective GAs (PISA)

highlighted the accuracy of the final Pareto front found by the algorithm as well as its efficiency. Two GAs methodologies have been selected for the comparison, Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA 2) and Non-dominated Sorting GA II (NSGA II) The said GA performance is comparable with the selected GAs. A quantitative metric has been defined. The results are illustrated in Fig. 2, as box whisker plots showing the quartiles of error. GA showed a better behavior in regard of convex problem and slightly but reasonably worse behavior concerning non-convex problem. Distribution of distances from the theoretical front in the last generation showed major points density around average value for GA, on the other hand commercial software resulted in a spreader distribution.

3. VARTM optimization

3.1 Materials and viscosity model

The cure kinetics and viscosity model for the resin used in this work (Hexcel RTM6) follow the work of Karkanis et al. [18;19]. The reaction rate can be described as:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_1(1-\alpha)^{n_1} + k_2\alpha^m(1-\alpha)^{n_2} \quad (1)$$

where α is fractional conversion and m , n_1 and n_2 reaction orders. The rate constants k_1 and k_2 take into account chemical and diffusion terms compounded as follows:

$$\frac{1}{k_i} = \frac{1}{k_{i,c}} + \frac{1}{k_d} \quad i = 1,2 \quad (2)$$

The chemical rate constants follow an Arrhenius dependence on temperature, while the diffusion part is expressed as stated in Eq 3.

$$k_d = A_d \exp\left(-\frac{E_d}{RT_c}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{b}{f}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$k_{ic} = A_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right) \quad i = 1,2 \quad (4)$$

Here T is the temperature expressed in Kelvin, E_1 , E_2 , E_d activation energies, A_1 , A_2 , A_d pre-exponential factors and R is the universal gas constant, b is a constant and f , given in Eq. 5, is the equilibrium fractional free volume:

$$f = 0.00048(T - T_g) + 0.025 \quad (5)$$

$$T_g = T_{g0} + \frac{(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1-\lambda)\alpha} \quad (6)$$

In Eq 6 T_{g0} is the glass transition of the uncured material and $T_{g\infty}$ the one of the full network, λ a model parameter. Thermal properties are based on experimental data presented in [14]. The specific heat of fibers and resin are respectively:

$$c_{pf} = 0.0023T + 0.765 \quad (7)$$

$$c_{pr} = 0.0025 + 1.8T + \frac{0.25}{1 + \exp(c(T - T_g - \sigma))} \quad (8)$$

The rule of mixtures has been applied to find the specific heat of composite:

$$c_p = w_f c_{pf} + (1 - w_f) c_{pr} \quad (9)$$

Here w_f is the fiber weight fraction. Combining Eq 7-9 yields:

$$c_p = A + BT + \frac{C}{1 + \exp(c(T - T_g - \sigma))} \quad (10)$$

The thermal conductivity of the composite for longitudinal and transverse direction is:

$$K_i = A_i + B_i T + C_i T \alpha^2 + D_i T \alpha + E_i \alpha^2 + F_i \alpha \quad (11)$$

Table 2 reports the values of coefficient for said material model.

The evolution of viscosity is described by the following equations [20]:

$$\ln \frac{\eta}{\eta_g} = -\frac{C_1(T_{cure} - T_r - T_g)}{C_2 + T_{cure} - T_r - T_g} \quad (12)$$

where $\eta_g = 10^{12}$ Pas, while the other parameters for RTM6 are:

$$T_r(^{\circ}C) = -145 + 1.239T_{cure} \quad (13)$$

$$\ln C_1 = 2.908 + 291.8T^{-1} \quad (14)$$

$$\ln C_2 = -5.485 + 3562T^{-1} \quad (15)$$

Where T_{cure} is the cure profile temperature. The infusion stage is modeled using Darcy's law:

$$\bar{u} = -\frac{\tilde{K}}{\eta} \cdot \nabla P \quad (16)$$

where \tilde{K} is the permeability tensor of the preform, P is the pressure and \bar{u} is the velocity vector.

3.2 Model Description

A 2D section of a C stiffener (Fig. 3.) has been chosen for the infusion optimization problem. The model has been built using PAM-RTM 2010 [22]. The materials were carbon fibres G1157 unidirectional and RTM6 epoxy resin. Table 3 reports permeability for the carbon fibres used, while Table 4 shows the density of both resin and fibres

The model is built with 1909 nodes and 2557 elements. The fibre volume fraction was set to 60%. The lay-up was [+45 -45]_{2s}. The porous medium was a PTFE coated glass fibre fabric, with fibre volume fraction of 25%, and permeability, equal to $10^{-10} m^2$. Material properties for the porous medium and steel block are reported in Table 5 [23].

Air convection condition has been used on the bag side of the model while fixed temperature boundary condition, dictated by the optimization, has been applied to the lower boundary part of the C stiffener; three feasible gate locations have been located.

The initial degree of cure has been set to 6% and initial fibres and tool temperature have been set equal to the initial temperature of the non-isothermal profile.

3.3 Optimization strategy

The goal of the optimization is to find the best gate location configuration, temperature profile during the filling of the part and initial resin temperature in order to minimize filling time and degree of cure at the end of the filling stage. A set of three feasible gates location is provided for the optimization. For every individual in the population the optimizer selects a gate location among the ones provided, initial resin temperature and a temperature profile determined by five parameters: temperature of first

and second dwell, duration of first and second dwell and duration of the ramp which can be either a ramp-up or down (Fig. 4). The two objectives taken into account deal with two aspects of the process: minimizing filling time which is related with process cost and the minimization of degree of cure at the end of the filling which is related to the quality of the final product and the likelihood of process failure.

Table 6 lists the parameters of the optimization and Table 7 the parameters ranges chosen. The duration of the second dwell has been assigned to a high value of time. This has been done to avoid having duration of the filling longer than the duration of the non-isothermal profile.

4. Results

Fig. 5 shows the results of the multi objective optimization depicting the Pareto front at different generations. The GA is able to approach the final Pareto set successfully showing a high rate of convergence, within 10 generations.

Since the Pareto front of the last generation only includes solution with gate number 3, it has been chosen to report only the standard results corresponding to this gate. Standard VARTM infusion for RTM6 epoxy resin is an isothermal filling in which the tool plate is kept at 120 °C and the resin is injected at 80 °C. Standard infusion results has a filling time equal to 582 s and a final degree of cure at the end of the cure equal to 0.11. The L-shape of the final Pareto set suggests a preferential direction towards the corner that allows to improve both filling time and degree of cure. Furthermore it highlights two distinct zones, the horizontal part and the vertical part. Moving along the horizontal part it is possible to achieve significant improvement in filling time while along the vertical part it is possible to achieve significant improvement in degree of cure. The standard isothermal infusion lies away from these two zones allowing improvements in either the objectives. Choosing a design point at the corner of the Pareto front it is possible to achieve a 42% reduction in filling time and a 14% reduction in final degree of cure. The resin temperature at this corner point is 115 °C while the temperatures of the first and second dwell are 157 °C and 159 °C respectively. This suggests that increasing the resin and dwell

temperature affect positively both filling time and degree of cure as long as the filling is fast enough to keep the reaction rate of the resin still at the beginning of its overall development.

An exhaustive search has been carried out in order to investigate the objective space of the problem. About 9000 evaluations have been carried out. Figs. 6-7 present a zoom in of the objective space in which is possible to compare the result of the GA optimization with the exhaustive search. The approximation achieved by the GA is very good. The Pareto front from the exhaustive search shows only one non-dominated solution not identified by the GA. Nevertheless it is important to highlight that the exhaustive search evaluation required about 15 times the computational required for the GA.

The objectives space of the design problem is illustrated in Figs. 8-11. Examination of the surface shows that the design parameters must be chosen carefully since the line between a successful infusion and an incomplete one, due to a viscosity increase, is subtle. Gate location and resin temperature in particular proved to be the most critical parameters concerning this. The irregular nature of the objective space, revealing the presence of some local minima, justify the choice of a GA.

4. Conclusion

The optimization procedure presented here can be used to optimize gate locations initial resin temperature and a non-isothermal temperature profile in a VARTM process in order to minimize filling time and degree of cure at the end of filling. The two objectives show a clear trade off resulting in L shape Pareto front. This typical shape gives the opportunity to select a certain combination of design parameters able to provide significant improvements, up to 42% of reduction, in both objectives with respect to the standard solution.

The exhaustive search undertaken provided a better understanding of the process pointing out the critical dependence of the objectives towards changes in initial resin temperature and gates location. Furthermore it highlighted the complex nature of the design space landscape proving that the problem studied has no trivial solutions bringing out therefore the efficiency, reliability and robustness of the GA used.

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Tables

Table 1. Input for benchmarks

Problem	Generation Number	Individual Population	Individual Reproduction	Chromosome Size	Elite
Schaffer	50	100	70	10	4
Zitzler-1	400	100	70	10	4
Zitzler-2	400	100	70	10	4
Fonseca	400	200	105	15	15

Table 2. Cure kinetics and thermal parameters for RTM6 and carbon fibres composite

Cure Kinetics	M	1.16	$A_1(s^{-1})$	17580	$E_2(Jmol^{-1})$	59050
	n_1	1.80	$A_2(s^{-1})$	21525	$A_d(s^{-1})$	6.48E+18
	n_2	1.32	$E_1(Jmol^{-1})$	70500	$E_d(Jmol^{-1})$	136800
	b	0.467	$T_{g0}(^{\circ}C)$	-11	$T_{g\infty}(^{\circ}C)$	206
	λ	0.435				
$c_p (J/^{\circ}C/Kg)$	$A(Jg^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	0.0024	$B(Jg^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	1.064	$C(Jg^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	-0.072
	$c(^{\circ}C^{-1})$	1.1	$\sigma(^{\circ}C)$	16.5		
K_l	$A_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	5.86	$B_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	4.36E-3	$C_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	3.2E-4
	$D_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	-4.4E-4	$E_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	-3.75E-2	$F_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	8.8E-2
K_t	$A_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	0.398	$B_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	4E-5	$C_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	-1.6E-4
	$D_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-2})$	2.2E-4	$E_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	1.87E-2	$F_i(Wm^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1})$	4.4E-2

Table 3. Permeability data

	Permeability(m ²)
K₁	6.0*10 ⁻¹³
K₂	2.5*10 ⁻¹³
K₃	4.0*10 ⁻¹⁵

Table 4. Density data

	Density (Kg/m ³)
Resin	1100
Fibre	1760

Table 5. Material properties

	Steel block	Porous media
ρ (Kg/m ³)	7900	2560
K (W/m*°C)	35	1.04
C_p (J/Kg*°C)	500	670

Table 6. Optimization parameters set-up

Number of generations	20
Individual per population	15
Individual per reproduction	10
Elite individuals	4
Size of Pareto	25
Mutation probability	0.005
Cross-over probability	0.5

Table 7. Design parameter ranges

Design Parameters	Range
t1 (s)	60-150
t2 (s)	90-210
t3 (s)	4000
T1 (°C)	120-190
T2 (°C)	120-190
T resin (°C)	70-140
Gate number	3

Figures

Schaffler

Zitzler-1

Zitzler-2

Fonseca

Fig. 1. Reproducibility tests for the four benchmarks

Fig. 2. Accuracy comparison between GA and PISA establish software

Fig. 3. C-section geometry and boundary conditions

Fig. 4. Non-isothermal filling: Temperature profile

Fig. 5. Pareto front at different generations

Fig. 6. Comparison between exhaustive search and Genetic Algorithm solution

Fig. 7. Objective space

Fig. 8. Filling time vs ramp and first dwell duration

Fig. 9. Degree of cure vs ramp and first dwell duration

Fig. 10. Filling time vs initial resin temperature and first dwell temperature

Fig. 11. Degree of cure vs gate location and initial resin temperature